

To study the healing effect of *Mahagouradya ghrita* in the management of non-healing infected wound w.s.r.to *Chirakalin dushta vrana*: A case study

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Abstract

Ayurveda is a branch of science which deals with maintaining healthy status and treating the diseased condition of the body. [1] It has eight branches namely *Kaya*, *bala*, *Graha*, *urdhwanga*, *Shalya*, *Drashta*, *Jara* and *Vrushan*. In today's modern world, everyone is less conscious towards the own health. Wound is the discontinuation of the skin. It is neglected due to busy schedule of the people and it attains the severe state. So it is the necessary of the body to heal the wound in well time. The modern science has a vast resource of antibiotics to cure the wound. It also prevents the further inflammation. But at some time, it fails to give the desired result. Here, our Ayurveda plays the vital role and restores the healthy status of skin. In this study, *Mahagouradya ghrita varti* is applied on the *Chirakalin dushta vrana* and its effect is assessed as very effective.

Keywords: Ayurveda; *Drushta*; *Vrana*; *Pichu*

1 Introduction

Wound is defined as discontinuity of skin or tissue.[2] Even if it has healed it leaves a scar, which stays as long as the person is alive. *Dushta Vrana* worsens the condition of the patient with different complications and may become fatal. In India, most of the population still resides in poor hygienic and malnourished conditions, so the incidence of infection is maximum and delayed ulcer healing is more common.

“In India, the prevalence of wound in the population studied (6917) is 15.03 per 1000”. [3] In today's modern world of civilisation, the occurrence of wound is neglected due to busy schedule. It results in the various infections of the wound and it is transformed into non – healing ulcer. It is called *Dushtavrana*.

According to modern science, wound healing is the series of various actions undergoing in the body to heal a wound. It is called as Wound healing Process. Bacterial infections in the wound breaks the healing process and ultimately results in serious complications. Due to this, it is necessary to heal this wound as soon as possible. Our main aim remains the same as to restore the function of the skin to achieve the possible cosmetic effect and to avoid as far as both early and late complications.

The most important things in the treatment for *dushta vrana* are time as well as good resisting power. *Acharya Sushruta* has mentioned two types of *vrana* namely *Nija Vrana* and *Agantuja vrana*. Of this, *nija vrana* is caused by *Doshaprakopa*. It results in the formation of *Vranavastha*. “It is formed by *Darana* of *Vranashotha* in *pakwavastha*. *Agantuja vrana* is formed due to trauma or injury”. [4]

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The *vrana* which is contaminated due to presence of *doshadushti* called *dushta vrana* (*Nija Vrana*). It is mainly characterized by presence of *Vedana* (pain), *Daha* (burning), *paka* (pus formation), *gandha* (foul odour), *Dushtashonita srava* (discharge) etc. The *vrana* which is free from any infection or *doshadushti* is termed as *Shuddha vrana*. *Acharya Sushruta* has explained 60 types of treatments for *Vrana* containing *Varti*, *Kalka*, *Sarpi*, *Taila*, *Rasakriya*, *Avachurana*, *Vrana dhupana* etc.

Ulcer management is a special emerging branch in the present era. Ayurveda has described various *Kalpas* in the management of *Vrana*. So with the new era, Ayurveda can contribute with its vast medicaments in ulcer healing. But the management of *vrana* especially *dushta vrana* is still a challenge. So present study is an attempt to review the use of *mahagouradya ghrita* described in the *Gadanigraha prayogakhanda ghritadhikar* in the management of *Dushta Vrana*.

2 Material and methods

Compilation of different reference form texts and *Samhita* related to topic.

Explore and elaborate the concept of *dushta vrana* by referring books, papers, *samhita* etc.

3 Review of literature

Mahagouradya ghrita is mentioned *Gadanigraha prayogakhanda ghritadhikar* in the management of *Dushta Vrana*. It is mentioned as *Sarva vranavishodhana* and *Vranaropana*.

Table 1 Content of Mahagouradya ghrita

Sr. No.	Drug Name ^[5]	Latin Name	Rasa	Veerya	Vipaka	Karma
1	<i>Daruharidra</i>	<i>Berberis aristata</i>	<i>Tikta, Kashaya</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Vranashodhana, Vranaropana</i>
2	<i>Nisha</i>	<i>Circum longa</i> Linn.	<i>Tikta, Katu</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Shothahar, Vedanasthapan</i>
3	<i>Manjishta</i>	<i>Rubia cordifolia</i> Linn.	<i>Tikta, Kashaya, Madhur</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Shothahar, Vedanasthapan</i>
4	<i>Jatamamsi</i>	<i>Nordastachys Jatamansi</i> DC	<i>Tikta, Kashaya, Madhura</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Dahaprashamana, Vedanasthapan</i>
5	<i>Kutaki</i>	<i>Picrorhiza kurroa royale</i>	<i>Tikta</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Bhedana, Deepana</i>
6	<i>Prapoundarik</i>	<i>Cassia tora</i> Linn.	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Lekhana, Kushthaghna</i>
7	<i>Yashtimadhu</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glaba</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Dahashyamaka, Vedanasthapan</i>
8	<i>Nagarmotha</i>	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	<i>Tikta, Katu, Kashaya</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Shothahara</i>
9	<i>Raktachandana</i>	<i>Pterocarpus santalinus</i>	<i>Tikta, Madhura</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Shothahara, Dahashamaka</i>
10	<i>Jatiphala</i>	<i>Myristica fragrans</i>	<i>Tikta, Katu</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Shothahara, Vedanasthapan</i>
11	<i>Nimba</i>	<i>Azadiracta indica</i>	<i>Tikta, Kashaya</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Vranapachana, Vranashodhana</i>
12	<i>Patola</i>	<i>Trichosanthes dioica</i> Roxb.	<i>Tikta</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Deepana, Aamapachana</i>
13	<i>Katphal</i>	<i>Myrica esculenta</i> Buch	<i>Kashaya, Tikta, Katu</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Shothahara, Kothaprashamana</i>

14	<i>Madhuchhishta</i>	<i>Adiantum caudatum</i> Linn.	<i>Tikta, kashaya, Madhura</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kushthaghna, Jwaraghna</i>
15	<i>Ghrita</i>	-	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Balya, Rasayana</i>
16	<i>Shir</i>	-	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Balya</i>

4 Case study- done after ethical committee approval

A 68 year old male, Hindu by religion, retired person after taking informed written consent for examination and clinical trial, selected for case study. he is presently living in *Sadharan desha* presented at the OPD of *Shalyatantra* Department having complaints of non healing wound over right foot ankle region from last 6 months with foul smell, thick purulent discharge, necrotizing tissue. The wound was size of 10 × 7 cm, 1.5 cm deep infected wound. He was come for further management.

K/C/O - Diabetes mellitus.

M/H/O – Metformin 500 mg BD before meal

H/O – Detriment two months before from outside.

Patient has used many other medicines for *Dushta vrana* which gave no permanent relief. On examination of the patient, vitals were within normal limits.

4.1 Diagnosis

The condition was diagnosed as *Chirakalin Drushta vrana*.

4.2 Equipment

Sterile swab, bowls, gloves, gauze piece, normal saline, sponge holder, Artery forceps, sterile pads, cotton, Bandage, sticking, Kidney tray, autoclave etc.

4.3 Treatment Method

Cleaning of wound with normal saline and application of *Mahagouradya ghrita* gauge packing on wound.

4.4 Duration and follow up of treatment

28 days. Daily upto 7 days, then alternate day upto 14 day, then once weekly upto 28th day.

Figure 1 Chirakalin Dusta vrana with dead tissue

Day 1

He was treated and status of the wound was as follows

- Debriment done. It results in the necrotizing tissue and all slough removed.
- All pus pockets drained.

- First wound washed with Betadine and Hydrogen peroxide. Then washed with normal saline.
- Then weight gauge with *Mahagouradya ghritha* kept on wound and pressure bandage is given.
- On First day, Tab Ultracet given at TID for pain management.

On day 1 to day 7, Daily dressing done by giving wash with normal saline and *Mahagouradya ghritha* gauge packing done. It resulted in healthy granulation, mild slough and pus collection.

Figure 2 Chirakalin Dusta vrana desloughing of dead tissue

Day 8

From Day 8 to day 14, dressing done by giving wash with normal saline and *Mahagouradya ghritha* gauge packing done with two alternate days. It resulted into mild slough but no pus observed.

Figure 3 Chirakalin Dusta vrana desloughing of dead tissue

Day 14

On day 21, dressing done by giving wash with normal saline and *Mahagouradya ghritha* gauge packing. It resulted into minimal slough but no pus. Healthy healing of wound.

Figure 4 Chirakalin Dusta vrana complete desloughing of pus and dead tissue Day 21

On 28th day, wound washed with normal saline and *Mahagouradya ghrita* gauge packing. It resulted into healing of wound.

Figure 5 Chirakalin Dusta vrana with healthy granulation with no slough

Day 28

5 Result

Table 2 Assessment of the treatment

Assessment Criteria	0th day	7th day	14th day	21th day	28th day
Vedana (pain)	+++	++	++	+	-
Vrana Parimana (size)	+++	+++	+++	++	+
Srava (Discharge)	++	++	+	+	-
Vrana Gandha (Baker in haight scale 1993)	+++	++	++	++	+

1. (+-mild ,++-moderate,+++ -severe); (- symbole Denotes no complaint)

6 Discussion

In today's era of Civilisation, the occurrence of wound is neglected due to busy schedule. It results in the various infections of the wound and it is transformed into non - healing ulcer. In this study *Mahagouradya ghrita* is used in the management of non-healing infected wound w.s.r.to *chirkalin Dushta Vrana*. It showed decrease in the severity of the assessment criteria like *Vedana*, *vrana parimana*, *srava* and *vrana gandha*. It has shown *vedanasthapak*, *Stravanashak*, *Shodhana* and *ropana* property in the management of *dushta vrana*.

7 Conclusion

It has significant effect on healing of *dushta vrana*. Raw drugs of *Mahagouradya ghrita* are easily available, cost effective, herbal contains and easy technique of Picchu. After wound healing, no any adverse reaction or complications found during study period.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

Ethical committee approval was done.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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